

Stellar and accretion properties of young stellar objects in a low-metallicity environment

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Abstract

We present preliminary results of a spectroscopic survey of young stellar object (YSO) candidates in a low-metallicity ($Z \sim 0.17 Z_{\odot}$) star forming region (SFR), located towards the Galactic anticentre. These YSO candidates were selected through mid-infrared Spitzer/IRAC data and optical/near-infrared catalogues. The survey, conducted with MODS at the Large Binocular Telescope (LBT; Arizona), aims at characterizing the accretion parameters and properties of the disk-bearing population in the region down to stellar mass $M_{\star} \sim 0.3 M_{\odot}$ to investigate the accretion disk evolution/lifetime and the star formation history of this SFR. The final goal is to understand if accretion in metal-poor environments lasts longer than previously thought. This kind of work can be considered as a testbench study for current space-based *JWST* observations of metal-poor environments in the outer Galaxy and in the Magellanic Clouds, as well as for soon to come observations and future ground-based facilities (e.g., MOONS, MORFEO, MAVIS).

1 Introduction

Infrared observations of young clusters with solar metallicity show that optically-thick circumstellar disks disappear in $\sim 1\text{-}3$ Myr in approximately half of young low-mass stars and are almost absent around members of $\sim 8\text{-}10$ Myr old associations (e.g., Fedele *et al.* 2010; Currie & Sicilia-Aguilar 2011; Manzo-Martínez *et al.* 2020). The age of $\sim 8\text{-}10$ Myr approximately corresponds to the shutdown of mass accretion (e.g., Calvet *et al.* 2005; Sicilia-Aguilar *et al.* 2005). The disappearance of gas and dust, the planetary building material, places stringent constraints on the timescale of planet formation (Ercolano & Clarke 2010). In fact, since the formation and evolution of stars and planets are strongly connected, learning about the properties of young stars and their circumstellar disks is key to understand planet formation (Morbidei & Raymond 2016). In the magnetospheric accretion scenario, a central low-mass star grows in mass over time through accretion of material from a circumstellar disk of dust and gas funneled by the stellar magnetic field (e.g., Koenigl 1991; Hartmann *et al.* 2016). In this context, metallicity may play an important role on the evolution of circumstellar disks and mass accretion rate.

Observational studies of young (~ 1 Myr) stellar populations in Galactic star forming regions (SFRs) at low metallicity ($Z \sim 0.1 - 0.3 Z_{\odot}$) indicate that metal-poor stars dissolve their disks significantly faster than solar-Z YSOs (Yasui *et al.* 2009, 2016). This would suggest that a low-metallicity environment may induce higher mass accretion rates and/or a very efficient external photo-evaporation of the circumstel-

lar matter due to UV and/or X-ray radiation from OB stars, which contributes to a rapid disk erosion. As a consequence, stars forming in a low-metallicity environment should experience disk dispersal on timescales less than 1 Myr, much shorter than in a solar metallicity environments.

At the same time, other studies performed using HST photometry in young open clusters of the Magellanic Clouds ($Z \sim 0.1 - 0.3 Z_{\odot}$), demonstrate that mass accretion rates decrease more slowly with time than what is observed in solar-metallicity SFRs (e.g., De Marchi *et al.* 2010, 2013; Biazzo *et al.* 2019; Carini *et al.* 2022) and forthcoming *JWST* findings seems to give support to this statement (G. De Marchi, priv. comm.).

These two types of results are apparently in contradiction, because the former foresees shorter timescales for the disk dispersal, and the latter longer timescales for the decrease of mass accretion rate (and in principle longer disk lifetime). However, these studies are not directly comparable because they scrutinize different properties. From the one side, the dust content of circumstellar disks is used as a proxy for the total mass of the disks and their lifetimes, while from the other side the infall of the more abundant inner gas onto the stars is used as proxy of the mass accretion rate.

The complete census of metal-poor YSOs in low-metallicity regions, like the one of the outer Galaxy studied in this work, is essential to perform a detailed investigation of mass accretion rate and to compare the results with similar spectroscopic studies led in solar metallicity galactic YSOs. This will allow us to investigate the star formation history

in different metallicity environments and to shed light about possible inconsistencies claimed in the literature.

2 A star forming region in the direction of the Galactic anticenter

Sharpless 2-284 (Sh 2-284; Sharpless 1959), at a distance of ~ 4.5 kpc from the Sun (e.g., Cusano *et al.* 2011; Negueruela *et al.* 2015), is a HII region excited by the UV radiation of massive OB stars within the young (~ 3 -6 Myr) open cluster Dolidze 25 (Turbide & Moffat 1993; Negueruela *et al.* 2015). Dolidze 25, with $Z \sim 0.17 Z_{\odot}$ (Lennon *et al.* 1990) is the SFR with the lowest metallicity in our Galaxy (Negueruela *et al.* 2015), and its association to Sh 2-284 implies that the latter is characterized by low-metallicity as well.

The region was observed by Spitzer/IRAC and through $[3.6]-[4.5]$ versus $[5.8]-[8.0]$ diagrams, Puga *et al.* (2009) identified class I and class II YSO candidates and scrutinized the possibility of sequential star formation of the region. However, a complete spectroscopic characterization of the pre-main sequence (PMS) population of Sh 2-284 is still lacking. We aim at studying the physical and accretion properties of the YSO population in the still poorly studied environment of this low-metallicity SFR and investigate relationships between accretion and stellar properties, and how they compare with those of solar-metallicity nearby YSO populations.

3 Candidate Selection and First Observations

Very recently, Guarcello *et al.* (2021) analyzed Chandra observations of the Dolidze 25 cluster and combined the resulting source catalogue with existing optical/infrared catalogues of the region, selecting a population of disk-bearing objects. We have obtained MODS@LBT observations of a sample of YSOs candidates selected from the catalogue of Guarcello *et al.* (2021). Figure 1 shows the location of the ~ 80 selected YSO candidates superimposed to the Spitzer/IRAC image, while Figures 2, 3, 4 show the position of our sample in the IPHAS $r - H\alpha$ versus $r - i$, 2MASS J versus $J - K$, and Spitzer $[3.6]-[4.5]$ versus $[5.8]-[8.0]$ diagrams.

Among the ~ 80 YSOs originally selected from the Guarcello *et al.* (2021) catalogue, a total of 56 targets ($\sim 70\%$) were observed with MODS from November 2021 and March 2022. The rest of the targets will be observed in the following months with the same instrument.

4 First Results

We started a preliminary analysis of the spectra of the observed targets. In Figure 5, we show the example of a MODS spectrum reduced with the SIPGI (Spectroscopic Interactive Pipeline and Graphical Interface) pipeline (Gargiulo *et al.* 2022) and obtained using both blue and red gratings. Emission lines, such as hydrogen Balmer and Paschen lines or Ca II lines, which are typical tracers of accreting YSOs, are clearly detected.

We measured the equivalent widths (EWs) and the integrated fluxes of several emission lines (e.g., Balmer, Paschen, Calcium, Helium). From our preliminary analysis, we identify 89% of the targets already observed as ‘legitimate YSOs’ on the basis of detection of accretion tracers, which gives support to our criteria for selecting accreting candidates.

Figure 6 shows the equivalent width of the $H\alpha$ line as a

Figure 1: Spitzer/IRAC image of the Sh 2-284 SFR. YSO candidates already observed with MODS are represented with filled magenta diamonds, while those to be observed are marked with empty yellow diamonds. The covered area is $\sim 50' \times 50'$. North is up and east to the left.

function of the optical and near-infrared colors ($r - H\alpha$, $J - K$, $[3.6]-[4.5]$, from the left to the right panel). Blue dots mark the position of the sources for which we detected emission of the CaII infrared triplet, while bigger dots represent targets with EW of the CaII line at $\lambda \sim 8662 \text{ \AA}$ greater than 3 \AA . Similar results are obtained also for the other two calcium infrared lines. Sources with greater values of $H\alpha$ equivalent width are those with calcium triplet lines in emission and with higher values of near-infrared colors. Most of them are also those with greater CaII EWs. This trend observed between the $H\alpha$ EWs (accreting diagnostics) and colors (disk diagnostics) could be related to the fact that objects with detectable accretion have optically thick inner disks. This issue will be exploited during our future analysis (Biazzo *et al.*, in prep.).

5 Future Perspectives

We will characterize the young population of this low-metallicity region in terms of physical parameters and accretion properties. In particular, we will: *i.* use the current and forthcoming MODS data to confirm the nature of the targets as legitimate class II YSOs; *ii.* measure, from the flux of several emission lines we will derive, the mass accretion rate of the objects with stellar mass down to $\sim 0.3 M_{\odot}$; *iii.* characterize the YSOs in terms of astrophysical properties; *iv.* investigate the YSO spectral energy distributions in order to get reliable estimates of the disk/envelope parameters. Finally, we will compare our results with recent findings obtained through similar spectroscopic methods for solar-metallicity SFRs in the solar vicinity (see, e.g., Alcalá *et al.* 2017, 2021; Gangi *et al.* 2022, and references therein).

Our research represents a pathfinder for current and forth-

Figure 2: IPHAS $r - H\alpha$ vs. $r - i$ color-color diagram. Small grey dots are all sources with good photometry falling in the field, red dots are the disk-bearing candidates, and blue dots represent our selection. Solid black lines are the ZAMS at various extinction values, dashed lines mark the locus of A_v stars as defined by Drew *et al.* (2005), while the solid green line is a ZAMS with $EW_{H\alpha} = 40 \text{ \AA}$ and $E_{B-V} = 1$, as defined by Barentsen *et al.* (2011).

coming studies of metal-poor environments with *JWST*. In fact, we are involved in observations of starburst clusters with low-metallicity within our Galaxy and in the Large/Small Magellanic Clouds. Our spectroscopic observations of the present study are complementary in terms of accretion diagnostics when compared to the *JWST* and therefore can be used as benchmark for studies aimed at understanding the nature of the mass accretion process in different environments, and how it depends on the stellar mass, age, and metallicity of the individual objects.

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Figure 3: 2MASS J vs. $J - K$ color-magnitude diagram. Symbols as in Fig. 2. Dashed lines show the isochrones for ages of 0.5, 1.5, 3, 5, 8, and 10 Myr (from top to bottom) and with metallicity $Z = 0.17 Z_{\odot}$ from PARSEC models (Bressan *et al.* 2012), plotted adopting a distance of 4.5 kpc and $A_V = 2.7$. We show also the loci expected to be populated by giants and foreground stars.

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Figure 4: Spitzer $[3.6] - [4.5]$ vs. $[5.8] - [8.0]$ color-color diagram. Symbols as in Fig. 2. The loci of stars with disks and stars with unreliable excesses are represented with red and green solid lines, as defined by Guarcello *et al.* (2021).

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Figure 5: Example of a MODS spectrum of a YSO candidate obtained with the blue ($\sim 320\text{-}590\text{ nm}$) and red ($\sim 540\text{ nm-}1\text{ mm}$) gratings. Emission of accretion diagnostics, such as $H\alpha$, $H\beta$, CaII infrared triplet, and $Pa\epsilon$ is evident, as marked within the plot.

Figure 6: Equivalent width of the $H\alpha$ line versus IPHAS $r - H\alpha$ (left), 2MASS $J - K$ (middle), and Spitzer $[3.6] - [4.5]$ (right) colors. Blue dots mark the sources with detected emission of the CaII infrared triplet lines. Bigger dots represent targets with EW of the CaII line at $\lambda \sim 8662\text{ \AA}$ greater than 3 \AA .